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Evaluation of Public City Branding Policies "Sparkling Surabaya"

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Abstract

Competition in the global era requires in every local government to have a competitive advantage to maintain its existence. The strategic solution in facing this competition is to strengthen the brand as the identity of a city. City Branding is the right step in completing the selling power of a city. Seeing the City of Branding in Surabaya is one of the policies of the City of Branding in Indonesia, it is necessary to evaluate the policy problems that have been taken. In terms of public policy, communication becomes important so that public policy can work and have an impact on development. This study looks at the level of awareness of the people of Surabaya in the City of Branding they already have. The method used is a survey method with a sample of 600 respondents. The results of this study indicate that the city policy of "Sparkling Surabaya" carried out by the Surabaya city government is carried out through efforts to maximize the use of communication and resources. The communication carried out by the Surabaya City government to introduce the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding generally uses billboards or billboards, in addition they also communicate through government offices and other public services. While the resources (resources) as a support of efforts to popularize the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" to the community. Resource facilities and infrastructure used for example, are media facilities for city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" to the public using television, radio, internet and other facilities and infrastructure. So that the existence of these resources can realize the effectiveness of policy communication that has been carried out to realize the success of the Surabaya City branding development. Because without the support of resources, the implementation of the city branding policy "Sparkling Surabaya" even though it has been well communicated to the target group but still will not run effectively.

Keywords: Public Policy, City Branding, Brand Awareness, Policy Evaluation

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Indonesia has a strong tourism potential with hundreds of local governments in it as tourism managers have the opportunity to become the country with the most tourism destinations for both domestic and foreign tourists. A

strong policy is needed, especially in developing the tourism sector not only in terms of infrastructure and accommodation but also in building images or trademarks of a city in order to win the development competition. Some experts define tourism as 'all activities in society related to tourists' (Soekadijo, 2000). Suwantoro (1997) defines tourism as a process of traveling temporarily from someone or more to another place outside of their place of residence. The drive to travel includes economic, social, cultural, political, religious, health interests, just being curious, adding experience or learning.

On the other hand, the challenges in this increasingly open age make interconnectivity between regions and information accessibility easier. That makes the cities of the world (including big cities in Indonesia) must compete with each other in attracting attention (influence), markets (markets), business & investment destinations (business & investment destinations), tourists (tourist), residents, skilled labor and also organizers of various events / events in the arts, sports and culture (Van Gelder, 2008 in Muktiali 2012). City branding is a process or an effort to form a brand of a city to facilitate the owner of the city to introduce/communicate the city to the target market (investors, tourists, talents, events) of the city by using sentence positioning, slogan, icon, exhibition, and various other media widely known (high awareness), accompanied by good perception. The purpose of city branding is to make the city widely known (high awareness) and get a good perception; so that it becomes a place for investment, tourist destinations, residential destinations, and organizing activities/events. Currently, the tourism marketing communication strategy by carrying out City Branding is indeed an activity that is very intensively carried out and greatly improved in its development, city branding has good prospects for shaping a positive image of a city as a tourist destination. The formation of city branding has been done for a long time in world cities, this is because many cities in the world have been prepared as tourism destinations that can be sold to local and international communities (Bungin, 2015 in Lubis 2018).

The implementation of city branding strategy itself is usually made in the form of slogans with artistic layout, in the sense of slogans that can represent a city itself. For example in Singapore with the brand Uniquely Singapore, from this slogan can explain and represent the city of Singapore, which has an image as a unique destination, namely a prosperous society and country, people living side by side, and building a strong nation. Destinations Singapore is a unique tourism object that is symbolized by a unique merlion statue, lion-headed, and a body of a mermaid, it is a unique and interesting creature. (Henderson in Bungin, 2015).

Since the end of 2005, Surabaya tourism actually has a city branding policy to support tourism marketing, namely "Sparkling Surabaya." The tagline in the early days became a policy that not only became a new Surabaya branding, but also reflected a tourism development strategy. Sparkling means shining and shining, it is hoped that all corners of the city will become tourism attractions. Starting from central Surabaya, west, east, north and south (Anshori and Satriya, 2008). Surabaya has a policy direction towards being an industrial city, trade, maritime, and education (abbreviated as Indamardi) which is rapidly advancing, certainly it needs carrying capacity in the tourism sector. Surabaya Mayor Decree No. 188.45 / 30 / 436.1.2 / 2006 concerning the Establishment of the Surabaya Tourism Promotion Board (STPB), a non-profit organization that has legality in promoting Surabaya tourism. "Simultaneously, completing STPB, Sparkling Surabaya city branding was launched" (Satriya, 2013: 14). STPB mobilizes branding awareness strategy for Sparkling Surabaya in various lines. Some of them are promotions on television, print media, brochures, videos, map making, websites, souvenirs, free magazines, holding roadshows, familiarization trips, cooperation with several universities and various parties to hold tourism events. Sparkling Surabaya has the tagline "You will love every corner of it." Through this tagline, it is implied by Arif Afandi's desire to make the whole city corner prima donna with its own uniqueness (Anshori et al., 2008: x). This concept appears in a 5-star visual that represents 5 sub-regions of Surabaya (north, east, west, south, and central Surabaya) on the Sparkling logo in Surabaya. The "Sparkling Surabaya" logo written in blue and green shows that Surabaya is located on the seafront and suggests that Surabaya is not hot in accordance with the city government's program to create a Surabaya Green and Clean. The green color also means many golf courses in various areas in Surabaya.

Logo Sparkling Surabaya

Marketing a city branding policy, a city is not only imaged through the process of strengthening infrastructure but also that city branding must be communicated to the community, both local people as "hosts" of migrants and visitors to the city of Surabaya, and in communicating them to the community, it is necessary to understand several concepts communication of a product to the community (Bungin, 2015: 76). In terms of public policy, borrowing the theory of the four factors that play a role in the implementation of a policy, according to Edward III (in Subarsono, 2006) communication, disposition, bureaucratic structure and resources are important collaborations for a policy. Without good communication between policymakers and policy implementers, public policy will not be able to run properly, ineffective, or even fail. This means that communication conveys a policy in the form of branding needs to be evaluated continuously. So it is interesting to study further about the performance of the implementation of City Branding Policy "Sparkling Surabaya" which could be increasingly forgotten by the people of Surabaya. As a basic argumentation building it is known that theoretically, an evaluation of public policy can be carried out as long as the policy is still carried out.).

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Public Policy

Public policy is one of the main studies of the science of state administration. According to Thoha (1983), the administration carries out the organizing function of the organization, including policy as a form of solving a problem on a particular issue. According Suharyanto (2006), Public policy exists when there are issues relating to public needs and demands, where public policy is intended to answer or solve the problems of an issue. Public policy is the government's decision to do or not do something in response to a problem. Woodrow Wilson in While Ripley (1985) in Subarsono (2006) explains that the stage of public policy starts from the preparation of the agenda (policy), policy formulation, policy implementation, and evaluation (of the implementation, performance and impact) of the policy, then from the evaluation policy can emerge new. While Nugroho (2008) describes the process of public policy through a looping mechanism that starts from the process of identifying policy issues, policy formulation, policy implementation and policy performance where the policy performance steps are also evaluated on the policy. Of the two opinions above, there are at least three main activities in the public policy process namely policy formulation, policy implementation and finally policy evaluation. From some of the expert opinions above, it can be understood that public policy is a response to a public problem in the form of a government decision or binding rules as a solution to the problem.

1.2.2 Evaluation of Public Policy

McQueen (2001) defines evaluation as a process that uses scientific methods to assess the implementation and outcomes of certain policies. Whereas Subarsono (2006) defines policy evaluation as an activity to assess the performance level of a policy. Subarsono added that the evaluation can be carried out after sufficient time has passed. Edward III (1980) in Subarsono (2006) holds that in evaluating a policy implementation there are four influential variables namely communication, resources (resources), disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The four variables can be explained further as follows:

1. Communication

Communication is about how to inform as easily as possible so that it can be understood by the target community about the aims and objectives of the policy taken.

2. Resources

Resources or resources in question is about the availability of financial resources, resources and adequate facilities. Without sufficient resources, the implementation of public policies, although well communicated to the target group, will still not be effective. Therefore, resources are an important factor that influences the successful implementation.

3. Disposition

Trends in the behavior or characteristics of the policy implementers play an important role in realizing implementation in accordance with the goals or objectives. Honesty and high commitment from policy implementers are important points in the successful implementation of policies. A good attitude will provide a better opportunity for effective implementation, while an attitude that does not support the implementation will not be implemented properly.

4. Bureaucratic Structure

The bureaucratic structure has a significant influence on the implementation of the policy, bearing in mind the bureaucracy as the implementor or implementer of the policy. There are two aspects in the organization, the first mechanism (usually in the form of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) which serves as a guideline for implementers) and the second aspect is the bureaucratic structure. The fatter and longer the flow of the bureaucracy in the organizational structure, the organizational activities cannot be flexible and reduce the efficiency of a policy.

1.2.3 City Branding

There are still many who confuse understanding of brand and branding. A brand is a brand that is owned by a company, while branding is a collection of communication activities carried out by the company in the framework of the process of building and growing a brand. Without communication activities to consumers that are well organized and planned, a brand will not be known and have no meaning to consumers or their target consumers (Maulana, 2008). Mukti (2012) cites Chaniago's opinion that city branding is a process or effort to form a brand of a city to make it easier for city owners to introduce their city to the target market (investors, tourists, talent, events) of the city by using positioning sentences, slogans, icons, exhibitions and various other media. While Pratikno, a lecturer at the University of Indonesia, defines city branding as the process of introducing a city that is represented on icons, ambassadors or events held in the city so that the city will be known as a unique city and different from other cities.

Meanwhile (Kawaratzis, 2007) stated that in city branding there are at least two aspects/dimensions that must be communicated to various parties. Both aspects/dimensions should be comprehensive, integrative, and integrated to support the image of a city/region to be better and more competitive. The main aspects/dimensions of city branding (primary communication) communication consist of 4 main aspects, namely landscape strategies (urban design, public space, public art), behavior (city vision, events, service quality), organizational (public private partnership)) and infrastructure. While the second dimension/aspect is in the form of publications and advertising, public relations, design and slogans. More can be seen in the picture below.

From the development of the spirit of city branding according to the picture above it can be seen that there is an important role in the primary process of communication, in addition to infrastructure support it also needs PPP (Public-Private Partnership) support, community networks and community participation. The structural role of organizations that live in a city branding building is very important considering that without the participation of the public and PPP (Public-Private Partnership) as well as existing community networks in the community becomes unsuccessful despite being encouraged and supported by large regional budgets even if they have to using third parties like advertising companies to increase the marketing impact of a city. From the picture above it can also be seen that primary communication has a greater role than secondary communication.

1.2.4 Brand Awareness

Brand Awareness or Brand Awareness is the main thing where companies compete to get a good impression of the products they produce. By reflecting a good impression of its products, consumers will always remember the brand of the product used. So consumers will realize that brands of similar products are marketed by other consumers. Therefore building brand awareness towards consumers is the most important thing in marketing a company. Brand awareness describes the existence of a brand in the minds of consumers which can be decisive in several categories. Increasing brand awareness is a mechanism for expanding brand markets. If brand awareness is low then it is almost certain that brand equity is low so it can be concluded that awareness is very important to build the perception and behavior of consumers in consuming a product. Measurement of brand awareness is based on levels of brand awareness, namely Top of Mind, Brand Recall, Brand recognition, Unaware of Brand. (David A. Aaker in Sianturi, 2010).

1. Top Mind; a condition which describes the brand that the respondent first remembers or is first mentioned when the person concerned is asked about a product category. Top of Mind is a single response question, meaning that one respondent may only give one answer to one question.

2. Brand Recall; a reminder is a reminder of a brand without assistance.

3. Brand Recognition; brand recognition is a minimum level of brand awareness, where brand recognition reappears after recollection through the help of brand recall.

4. Unaware of Brand; not realizing a brand is the lowest level in the brand awareness pyramid, where consumers are not aware of a brand.

In this case we associate promotional activities that we do, mainly advertising with consumer responses to our brand. Consumer responses include: Awareness (brand awareness), Comprehend (understanding the content of advertising messages by consumers), Interest (interest in products), Intentions (interest to buy), and finally Action

(actual buying actions). Consumer response becomes small because of the low consumer response to a brand (poor response). If illustrated in a diagram like below:

2. Research Method

2.1 Operational Research Variables and Definitions

This study consists of one variable, namely Brand Awareness:

- Operational Definition of Brand Awareness, namely public awareness as part of the city branding policy in seeing the brand "Surabaya Sparkling."
- The five dimensions used to see the level of awareness of city branding are Top of Mind (the first brand to remember), Brand Recall (Slogan / Image of the City Branding Logo), Brand recognition (knowledge of tourist destinations, sources of information), Unaware of Brand (Brand Loyalty)..

2.2 Sampling Procedures

Population is an object or subject in a group of individuals who have the same characteristics (Creswell, 2013). The population in this study is the entire population of the City of Surabaya, which is 2,885,555 (in 2018). A sample is a group of objects or subjects in a study selected from the population (Creswell, 2013). The sampling method in this study is included in the type of probability sampling, with the type of sampling design is simple random sampling. The reference made is based on the Yamane table (1967). In this study, consider using a precision level of $\pm 5\%$ so that the number of samples to be used is a minimum of 400. In this study a sample of 600 respondents will be used throughout the sub-district in the city of Surabaya.

2.3 Data Type and Analysis Techniques

The type of data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Where primary data is obtained directly from respondents by distributing questionnaires, while secondary data are data obtained from indirectly or interviews with relevant service officials and documentation data. The analysis technique used in this research is descriptive analysis and hypothesis testing using SPSS Software. Descriptive analysis is to describe and explain the demographic characteristics of the respondents relating to the variables studied (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Descriptive analysis is also used to describe the tendency of respondents' perceptions of questions as a measurement of variables

3. Results

From the results of research that has been carried out produces data which is then processed and analyzed based on the distribution of questionnaires in each sub-district in the city of Surabaya regarding the evaluation of the

"Sparkling Surabaya" city branding public policy which is presented in accordance with categories based on respondents' identities and finding data. The respondents' identity categories consisted of age, sex, last education level, sub-district origin and length of stay in the city of Surabaya. Then the findings data category consists of awareness of Surabaya city branding, the number of understanding of Surabaya city branding, the popularity of city branding in Indonesia, the city branding association "Sparkling Surabaya", the knowledge number of the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo, the last time knowing / seeing the logo "Sparkling Surabaya ", And the media to popularize " Sparkling Surabaya ", as well as public services and" Sparkling Surabaya ". The results of the study are explained in the tables below:

3.1 Identity of the Respondents

3.1.1 Age

The following are the results of questionnaire distribution to respondents by age, explained in the table:

Table 3.1.1 Distribution of Respondents by Age

	Age	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<21 (Gen Z)	168	28.0	28.0
	21-39 (Millennial)	218	36.3	64.3
	39-59 (Gen X)	170	28.3	92.7
	>59 (Baby Boomers)	44	7.3	100.0
	Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the above data it can be seen that from 600 people the number of respondents, the most are at the age of Millennial Generation that is 218 respondents or 36% and for Generation Z and Generation X respondents are 28% where Generation Z respondents are 168 people and Gen X respondents there are 170 people, while for the Baby Boomers Generation, there are 44 people or 7%.

3.1.2 Gender

The following are the results of questionnaire distribution to respondents based on the sex of the respondent, explained in the table:

Table 3.1.2 Distribution of Respondents by Genders based on the sex of the respondent, explained in the table:

	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Men	250	13.9	41.7
	Women	350	19.4	58.3
	Total	600	33.3	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above data it can be seen that from the number of respondents a total of 600 people consisted of 41.7% male respondents or a number of 250 people and female respondents numbered 350 people or as much as 58.3%. So it can be seen that respondents in the distribution of this questionnaire are dominated by women.

3.1.3 Latest Education

The following are the results of the distribution of questionnaires to respondents based on the respondent's last education level as follows:

Table 3.1.3 Distribution of Respondents by Latest Education

	Last Education	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Primary School	64	3.6	10.7
	Junior High School	106	5.9	17.7
	Senior High School	346	19.2	57.7
	College	84	4.7	14.0
	Total	600	33.3	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above data it can be seen that the number of respondents totaling 600 is dominated by respondents with a high school education level of 346 people or a number of 19.2% of the total respondents, while respondents with elementary education only numbered 64 people or as many as 3.6% and respondents who have a junior high school education of 10.7%. Then respondents with tertiary education level amounted to 84 people or as much as 4.7%. So that it can be seen that from the last education level all respondents are present, indicating that the last education level of the respondents is in the medium category.

3.1.4 Respondent by District List

The following are the results of the distribution of questionnaires to respondents based on the location of each district contained in the city of Surabaya, as follows:

Table 3.1.4 Distribution of Respondents by District

	District	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bubutan	21	3.5	3.5
	Genteng	14	2.3	5.8
	Simokerto	20	3.3	9.2
	Tegalsari	22	3.7	12.8
	Asemrowo	9	1.5	14.3
	Benowo	13	2.2	16.5
	Lakarsantri	11	1.8	18.3
	Pakal	11	1.8	20.2
	Sambikerep	12	2.0	22.2
	Suko Manunggal	22	3.7	25.8
	Tandes	19	3.2	29.0
	Dukuh Pakis	12	2.0	31.0
	Gayungan	9	1.5	32.5
	Jambangan	10	1.7	34.2
	Karang Pilang	15	2.5	36.7
	Sawahan	42	7.0	43.7
	Wiyung	14	2.3	46.0
	Wonocolo	17	2.8	48.8
	Wonokromo	33	5.5	54.3
	Gubeng	28	4.7	59.0
	Gunung Anyar	9	1.5	60.5
	Mulyorejo	17	2.8	63.3
	Rungkut	22	3.7	67.0
	Sukolilo	22	3.7	70.7
	Tambaksari	46	7.7	78.3
	Tenggilis Mejoyo	12	2.0	80.3
	Bulak	9	1.5	81.8
	Kenjeran	32	5.3	87.2
	Krembangan	24	4.0	91.2
	Pabean Cantikan	18	3.0	94.2
Semampir	35	5.8	100.0	
	Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it can be seen that the number of respondents 600 people have spread across all districts in Surabaya. It can be seen that the highest number of respondents is from Tambaksari Subdistrict, which is 46 people or as much as 7.7% while the smallest number of respondents are respondents from Bulak District, Gunung Anyar District, Gayungan District, and Asemrowo District which are 9 respondents or as many as 1.5%.

3.1.5 Length of Stay

The following are the results of the distribution of questionnaires to respondents based on their length of stay in Surabaya, as follows:

Table 3.1.5 Distribution of Respondents by Length of Stay in the City of Surabaya

Length of Stay	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1-10 Tahun	58	9.7	9.7
11-20 Tahun	235	39.2	48.8
21-30 Tahun	136	22.7	71.5
31-40 Tahun	85	14.2	85.7
41-50 Tahun	54	9.0	94.7
51-60 Tahun	21	3.5	98.2
>60 Tahun	11	1.8	100.0
Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from 600 respondents there shows that the distribution of respondents' length of stay in the city of Surabaya is between 11 years and 20 years, 235 people or 39.2% and the least respondents live in the city of Surabaya is over 60 years that is 11 people or as much as 1.8% of the total number of respondents. It can be said that respondents, in general, have lived in Surabaya for quite a long time^{3.2}

3.2 Data Finding

3.2.1 Awareness City Branding Surabaya

The following are the findings data from the distribution of questionnaires based on the awareness city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" according to residents of Surabaya, as follows:

Table 3.2.1 Surabaya City Branding by Surabaya Population

	City Branding	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Surabaya the Smart City	146	24.3	24.3
	Sparkling Surabaya	234	39.0	63.3
	Surabaya Kota Maritim	48	8.0	71.3
	Surabaya Indahmardi	34	5.7	77.0
	Bangga Surabaya	138	23.0	100.0
	Total		600	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the data table above, it can be seen that from 600 respondents there shows that the most awareness respondents about city branding in Surabaya City are "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding, which is 234 people or 39% of the total respondents while respondents with the least awareness is about the city branding "Surabaya Indahmardi" which is 34 people or 5.7%. This shows that respondents, in general, have an awareness of the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya."

3.2.2 Figures of Understanding of Sparkling Surabaya

The following are findings data from the distribution of questionnaires based on the respondents' understanding of the Surabaya community on the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding, as follows:

Table 3.2.2.a Figures for Respondents' Understanding

Figures of Understanding of Sparkling Surabaya	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Never Seen or Hear Sparkling Surabaya	166	27.7	27.7
At Least Ever See Logo or Have Heard Sparkling Surabaya	156	26.0	53.7
have seen and heard of "Sparkling Surabaya"	278	46.3	100.0
Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from 600 respondents there are 278 people or 46.3% have seen and heard of "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding, while respondents with 156 people or 26% at least have see the logo or have heard of city branding "Sparkling Surabaya." This shows that based on the number of understanding of the existence of city branding "Sparkling Surabaya," respondents, in general, are quite understanding.

The following will also be explained in the data findings based on the level of understanding of the city branding respondents "Sparkling Surabaya" in the table below:

Table 3.2.2.b Level of Understanding of Sparkling City Branding Surabaya

	Level of Understanding	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Do Not Understand	304	50.7	50.7
	Understand	296	49.3	100.0
	Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from 600 respondents, there show 304 respondents or as many as 50.7% do not understand about city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" while the other 296 respondents namely 49.3% have understood about city branding "Sparkling Surabaya." So it can be seen that the level of understanding of respondents, in general, has never heard or seen about the term Sparkling Surabaya. But the respondents did not understand the purpose and objectives of Surabaya Sparkling City Branding.

3.2.3 City Branding Popularity in Indonesia Following are the findings data from the distribution of questionnaires Based on the popularity of city branding in Indonesia as follows:

Table 3.2.3 Most Familiar City Branding in Indonesia

City Branding in Indonesia	Frequency	Valid Percent
Sparkling Surabaya	318	18.9
Bali the Island of Gods/Pulau Dewata	252	15.0
Beautiful Malang	216	12.8
Shining Batu	192	11.4
Jogja Never Ending Asia	132	7.8
Kediri Lagi	136	8.1
Banyuwangi The Sunrise of Java	116	6.9
Enjoy Jakarta	74	4.4
Impressive Probolinggo City	22	1.3

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from the total number of respondents, there are 318 respondents or 18.9% most familiar with Sparkling Surabaya. Whereas the most unfamiliar city branding among respondents is the city branding about Impressive Probolinggo City, which is 22 people or 1.3% of the total number of respondents. Then it can be seen that city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" is the best known or most familiar city branding in other cities/regencies in Indonesia. This can describe that as city branding, "Sparkling Surabaya" has succeeded in introducing the city of Surabaya among the people.

3.2.4 Sparkling City Branding Association Surabaya

The following are the data findings from the distribution of questionnaires based on the thoughts that crossed the respondents when they heard the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" as follows:

Table 3.2.4 Thoughts That Come to Respondents When Listening the Sparkling Surabaya branding

Thoughts That Crossed	Frequency	Valid Percent
Hotel	18	3.1
Business	42	7.2
Performance / Festival / Folk Party	98	16.8
Tourism	254	43.6
A sparkling, bustling and lively city	168	28.9
Total	600	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from the 600 respondents there show that that crossed the mind of 254 or as many as 43.6% of respondents when they heard the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" was to consider Surabaya as a tourism city, then 168 or around 28.9% respondents answered Surabaya as a city that was sparkling, lively and lively. Whereas only 18 or around 3.1% of respondents thought that "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding was related to the world of hospitality. This shows that most respondents when they heard and saw about "Sparkling Surabaya" then what crossed their mind was about Surabaya City as a tourist destination, so it can be said that the purpose of using the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" has had an impact on society in the introduction of the City Surabaya as a tourist destination.

3.2.5 Knowledge Figures of Sparkling Surabaya Logo

The following are the findings data from the distribution of questionnaires to respondents based on the knowledge figures of the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo in the table below:

Table 3.2.5 Knowledge Figuers About Sparkling Logo Surabaya

Knowledge Figures	Frequency	Valid Percent
UnFamiliar	184	30.8
Familiar	414	68.9
Total	600	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the table data above, it can be seen that from 600 respondents there are 414 respondents or around 68.9% claiming to be familiar with the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo, while 184 or around 30.8% of respondents are unaware or unfamiliar with the "Sparkling logo" Surabaya." So it can be said that in general, the people of Surabaya City have known of the existence of the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo.

3.2.6 Last Time Knowing / Seeing the Sparkling Surabaya Logo

The following are the findings data from the distribution of questionnaires to respondents based on the knowledge number of the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo in the table below:

Table 3.2.6 Last Knowing / Seeing the Surabaya Sparkling Logo

Last Time Knowing	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
The Past 1 Year	292	69.5	69.5
The Past 1-3 Year	108	25.7	95.2
Over The Past 3 Year	20	4.8	100.0
Total	420	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the data table above it can be seen that from the 600 total respondents, 292 or around 69.5% said that the last time they knew or saw the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo was within the past 1 year, then 108 people or around 25.7% of respondents said that they knew or saw the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo for the past 1-3 years while 20 respondents had known or seen the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo over the past three years. This shows that the intensity of the community in knowing or seeing the "Sparkling Surabaya" logo is already quite high, as evidenced by their time period in knowing or seeing the logo.

3.2.7 Media for popularizing Sparkling Surabaya

The following are the data findings from the results of the distribution of respondents questionnaire based on the media to popularize "Sparkling Surabaya" in the table below:

Table 3.2.7 Media City Branding Sparkling Surabaya

	Media	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Print Mass Media	62	14.7	14.7
	Billboards	212	50.2	64.9
	Radio / Television / Internet	28	6.6	71.6
	Government Office / Public Service	120	28.4	100.0
	Total		100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the data table above it can be seen that of the 600 existing respondents, 212 respondents or around 64.9% answered that the media used to popularize the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" was through billboards or billboards, then 120 respondents answered that media were used to popularize city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" was popularized through government offices / public services. Furthermore, 62 respondents or around 14.7% said that the effort to popularize the city branding was carried out through print media. While only 28 respondents said that the effort to popularize was done through radio, television or the internet. So that it can be said that the effort to popularize city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" is generally done using billboards or billboards.

3.2.8 Public Service and Sparkling Surabaya

The following are the data findings from the results of the distribution of respondent questionnaires based on the level of interrelation between public services and "Sparkling Surabaya" in the table below:

Table 3.2.8 Relationship between Public Service and Sparkling Surabaya

	Statement	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not Reflect "Sparkling Surabaya"	116	24.6	24.6
	Reflected Surabaya	356	75.4	100.0
	Total	600	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the data table above, it can be seen that out of 600 respondents, 356 respondents or around 75.4% said that public services reflected "Sparkling Surabaya" and 116 respondents or around 24.6% said that public services did not reflect "Sparkling Surabaya." So it can be concluded that the existence of the city branding has provided a view to the wider community, especially the people of Surabaya City, on every public service provided by the Surabaya city government on various aspects, for example services in terms of tourism activities.

4. Discussion

Based on the above research, a discussion of research on the evaluation of the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding public policy will be elaborated. Edward III (1980) in Subarsono (2006) holds that in evaluating a policy implementation there are four influential variables namely communication, resources (resources), disposition, and bureaucratic structure. City Sparking Surabaya's branding efforts by the city of Surabaya, in general, tend to maximize the use of communication and resources. Communication as a way of informing the "Sparkling Surabaya" branding is as easy as possible so that it can be recognized and understood by the people of Surabaya City as the object of the purpose and objectives of the policy taken. While the resources (resources) as a support of efforts to popularize the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" to the community. The resources referred to in this case for example concerning the availability of financial resources, adequate resources and infrastructure facilities. Sufficient facilities and infrastructure resources, for example, are media facilities used to communicate "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding to the public using billboards or billboards, television, radio, internet and other facilities and infrastructure. So that with these resources can realize the effectiveness of policy communication that has been carried out to realize the success of the Surabaya City branding development.

Furthermore, the discussion in this study will be based on analysis using the results of data processing and the theoretical approach used as follows:

a. Awareness city branding "Sparkling Surabaya"

Brand Awareness or Brand Awareness is the main thing where companies compete to get a good impression of the products they produce. By reflecting a good impression of its products, consumers will always remember the brand of the product used, as well as brand awareness about "Sparkling Surabaya" that has been made by the Surabaya City government as an effort to reflect a good impression on the wider community for what is in City of Surabaya. If you see from the results of data processing, then it is in accordance with what was stated by respondents that 234 people or as many as 39% of the total respondents had awareness of city branding in the city of Surabaya while only a few of the respondents had awareness about the city branding "Surabaya Indahmardi" namely a number of 34 people or 5.7%. This shows that the efforts of the Surabaya City government to build brand awareness to the community are quite successful because the brand awareness in this city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" has illustrated the existence of the brand in the minds of the people. In addition awareness is considered very important to build public perception and behavior in consuming a product produced by the City of Surabaya.

b. Figure of understanding of city branding "Sparkling Surabaya"

The number of understanding of a city branding can be measured through measurement of brand awareness. According to David A. Aaker in (Sianturi, 2010) measurement of brand awareness is based on levels of brand awareness, namely Top Of Mind, Brand Recall, Brand recognition, Unaware of Brand. If you see from the results

of data processing, it shows that respondents numbered 278 people or as many as 46.3% had seen and heard of "Sparkling Surabaya," while 156 respondents or 26% had at least seen a logo or had heard of "Sparkling Surabaya." So it can be stated that the understanding of city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" in general is sufficient to understand, but the respondents do not understand the intent and purpose of the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya." This can be seen from the level of measurement of brand awareness, that the presence of city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" is at the level of top mind which is a condition where "Sparkling Surabaya" has described the brand that was first remembered by the public or first called when the concerned (community) was asked about a product category related to the city of Surabaya.

c. "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding association

The city branding association "Sparkling Surabaya" in this case, saw what thoughts crossed the minds of the people of Surabaya (in this case as research respondents) when hearing the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya." Because what has emerged so far in the minds of the people of Surabaya City are many things, for example, Surabaya as a tourism city, a business city, performances/festivals/ public parties, and the world of hospitality as well as a sparkling, bustling and lively city. If you look at the results of data processing, it shows that that crossed the mind of 254 people or as many as 43.6% of respondents when they heard the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" was to consider the city of Surabaya as a tourism city, some other respondents then considered the city of Surabaya as a city sparkling, lively and lively and only 18 people or about 3.1% of respondents who heard the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" is to consider the city of Surabaya related to the world of hospitality. This shows that the majority of respondents named the Surabaya community when hearing and seeing about "Sparkling Surabaya" then what crossed their mind was about Surabaya City as a tourist destination, so it can be said that the purpose of using the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" has had an impact on the public at the introduction of the City of Surabaya as a tourist destination.

d. Media to popularize "Sparkling Surabaya"

Muktiali (2012) cites Chaniago's opinion that city branding is a process or effort to form a brand of a city to make it easier for city owners to introduce their city to the target market (investors, tourists, talent, events) of the city by using positioning sentences, slogans, icons, exhibitions and various other media. The City Government of Surabaya, in this case, has carried out promotion as an effort to popularize the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding through various media. If you see from the results of data analysis that 212 of the 600 respondents or around 64.9% answered that the Surabaya City government tends to use billboards or billboards to popularize the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" then the effort to introduce is also done through government offices / public services. While only 28 respondents said that the effort to popularize was done through radio, television or the internet. So it can be said that to popularize the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding, the Surabaya City government generally uses billboards or billboards. It can be seen that promotional activities that can be carried out, mainly through advertising to cause consumer responses, namely the community towards the city branding owned by the City of Surabaya. These responses include awareness (brand awareness), comprehend (understanding the contents of advertising messages by consumers), interest (interest in products), intentions (interest in buying), and finally action (actual buying action).

e. Public services and "Sparkling Surabaya"

City branding "Sparkling Surabaya" is a public policy product owned by the Surabaya City government. With the "Sparkling Surabaya" is expected to give a good impression in the public's memory about the city of Surabaya. Neither with public service as an effort to provide services to the general public as consumers or service users who have the aim to realize public satisfaction. Services consist of various types of services, for example in administrative services, education services, economic services, tourism services and other fields. When viewed from the results of data processing it can be stated that 356 respondents or around 75.4% said that public services had reflected "Sparkling Surabaya" and 116 respondents or around 24.6% said that public services did not reflect "Sparkling Surabaya." So that it can be concluded that the existence of the city branding has provided a view to the wider community, especially the people of the City of Surabaya to every public service provided by the government of the City of Surabaya on various aspects, for example, services in terms of tourism activities.

5. Conclusion

From the results of the data analysis and discussion above, it can be concluded that the city branding efforts of "Sparkling Surabaya" carried out by the Surabaya city government generally tend to maximize the use of communication and resources. Communication as a way to inform the "Sparkling Surabaya" branding is as easy as possible. This was done in order to be able to be understood by the people of Surabaya about the purpose and objectives of the policy taken.

The communication carried out by the Surabaya City government to introduce the "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding generally uses billboards or billboards, in addition they also communicate through government offices and other public services. This can be seen where "Sparkling Surabaya" has become a brand that is first remembered by the public or first called when the concerned (community) is asked about a product category related to the City of Surabaya. So that the efforts of the Surabaya City government to build a brand to the community are quite successful because this brand awareness about the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" has illustrated the existence of the brand in the minds of the people.

While the resources (resources) as a support of efforts to popularize the city branding "Sparkling Surabaya" to the community. The intended resource is, for example, about financial resources, adequate infrastructure and resources. Sufficient facilities and infrastructure resources, for example, are media facilities used to communicate "Sparkling Surabaya" city branding to the public using television, radio, internet and other facilities and infrastructure. So that with these resources can realize the effectiveness of policy communication that has been carried out to realize the success of the Surabaya City branding development. Because without the support of resources, the implementation of the city branding policy "Sparkling Surabaya" even though it has been well communicated to the target group but still will not run effectively.

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